

INVESTIGATION OF TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCIES OF ELECTROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ CRYSTALS

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Abstract

Based on an experimental study of the temperature dependences of electrical conductivity, coefficients Hall and thermo-electromotive force of $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ crystals, the fundamental parameters of a semiconductor are determined: forbidden zone width, type of conductivity, concentration and mobility of free carriers.

Keywords: electrical conductivity, temperature, Hall coefficient, electro physical properties.

With the help of differential thermal, X-ray phase and microstructural analyzes of the SnTe-PrTe system, the state diagram was established and it was determined that solubility is observed in this system in the range of 0÷6 mol.% PrTe . There was no information about the study of the electro physical properties of crystals found in this interval. In the present work, the electro physical properties of solid solutions obtained in the $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ system have been studied. On fig. 1 shows the experimental results of the temperature dependence of the specific electrical conductivity of $\text{Sn}_{0.97}\text{Pr}_{0.01}\text{Te}$ - $\text{Sn}_{0.96}\text{Pr}_{0.04}\text{Te}$ solid solutions in the temperature range 100÷450K. And in Fig. 2 shows the experimental results of the temperature dependence of the Hall coefficients in the same temperature range. As can be seen from the figures, when the temperature changes in the range of 100÷360K, the electrical conductivity of both crystals decreases, and the Hall coefficient increases anomalously. Starting from 360 K temperatures, the electrical conductivity of these crystals increases, while the Hall coefficients decrease. At the temperature at which the electrical conductivity begins to increase, the concentration of free charge carriers takes on a rather high value of 10^{19} cm^{-3} , and at 450 K the concentration value increases and reaches a value of $3.1 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. With the exception of the low-temperature region, changes in the electrical conductivity and Hall coefficients of the above solid crystals at high temperatures confirm each other.

When the temperature changes from 100 to 450K, the specific electrical conductivity of crystals decreases and from 470K, it increases due to the onset of specific conductivity. In the mentioned temperature interval, the Hall coefficient, including the concentration of free charge carriers ($1.2 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), remains stable, and then it decreases due to the onset of specific conductivity. In other words, the dependencies $\sigma(T)$ and $R(T)$ of the above solid solutions confirm each other quite well.

Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 show the temperature dependences, respectively, of the coefficient thermo- electromotive force and the Hall mobility of charge carriers crystals $\text{Sn}_{0.97}\text{Pr}_{0.01}\text{Te}$ - $\text{Sn}_{0.96}\text{Pr}_{0.04}\text{Te}$.

As can be seen from fig. 3, the thermo- electromotive force coefficients of these crystals increase from 85 $\mu\text{V/d}$ to 150 $\mu\text{V/d}$ as the temperature changes from 300K to 400K.

From 400K, there is a decrease in the thermo- electromotive force coefficient. As can be seen from these dependences, the dependence $\mu(T)$ has a characteristic form for additive semiconductors.

That is, when the temperature rises from 100K to 200K, the mobility increases due to the scattering of charge carriers from impurity ions, and then, when the temperature changes from 300K, it decreases due to the scattering of charge carriers from thermal vibrations of atoms. At room temperature, the carrier mobility for these crystals is $\approx 200 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V} \cdot \text{s}$.

As can be seen from Fig. 3, with an increase in temperature in the range of 300÷350K, the thermo- electromotive force coefficient for these crystals increases in the region of impurity conductivity. This dependence is characteristic of semiconductors with a complex band structure. That is, at low temperatures, α should increase depending on the temperature due to a constant concentration, and at high temperatures, α should decrease due to a sharp increase in the number of intrinsic (main) electrons.

It should be noted that with an increase in the amount of Pr in $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ crystals, the electrical conductivity increases, while the Hall coefficient and thermo- electromotive force coefficient decrease.

The composition-dependent analysis of the forbidden zone width, determined based on the high-temperature $\lg \sigma = f(10^3/T)$ and

$\lg RT^{3/2} = f(10^3/T)$ dependences of the crystals detected in the $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ system, was also carried out.

The analysis of the temperature dependences of the specific electrical conductivity, Hall, thermo- e.m.f., shows that for all the studied crystals, as the temperature increases in the region of additional conductivity, the decrease of σ , the beginning of the specific conductivity, that is, the transition from the valence zone to the conduction zone. The increase stops due to the transfer of free electrons. In these crystals, the Hall coefficient and partly thermo- electromotive force in the temperature dependences of the coefficient, anomalies characteristic of substances with a complex zone structure, an increase in R and α are observed.

This increase can be explained based on the complex zone structure of the studied crystals, that is, the valence zone is composed of two additional zones formed by heavy and light holes.

In the presence of heavy holes, the Hall coefficient is determined as follows.

$$R = \frac{A}{ec_o} \cdot \frac{p_1\mu_1^2 + p_2\mu_2^2}{(p_1\mu_1 + p_2\mu_2)^2} = R_0 \frac{(1 + p_2/p_1)[1 + (p_2/p_1)b']^2}{[1 + (p_2/p_1)b']^2} \quad (1)$$

$$b' = \mu_2 / \mu_1$$

where the $R_0 = \frac{A}{pec_o}$ - Hall constant at low temperatures, $p = p_1 + p_2$, p_1 and p_2 are the concentrations of heavy and light holes, respectively.

It should be noted that R_{max}/R_0 depends only on the ratio of carrier mobility in the bands and does not depend on their energy difference.

If $b' = \frac{\mu_2}{\mu_1}$ is weakly dependent on temperature, then the Hall constant mainly depends on the distribution of charge carriers in the additional zones that make up the valence band.

The very low mobility of holes in the second zone, $\mu_2 < \mu_1 \ll 1$, has little effect on the Hall effect, and the concentration of free charge carriers decreases due to the transition of holes to the second zone

$$R = \frac{A}{ecp_2} \quad (2)$$

and thus the Hall constant rises sharply. Since the Hall constant takes its maximum value in the case of $p_1=p_2$

$$R_{max} = R_0 \frac{4b'^2}{(1+b')^2} \quad (3)$$

relationship is easily obtained based on the two-zone model.

The fact that the studied substances have a complex zone structure, their thermo- electromotive force it also manifests itself in the study of its coefficients. Thus, for $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ crystals, with an increase in temperature, thermo- electromotive force first increases and then decreases. This dependence can be explained as follows. According to the two-zone model, thermo- electromotive force coefficient is defined as follows.

$$\alpha = \frac{\alpha_{p_1} \cdot b' \cdot p_1 + \alpha_{p_2}}{b'p_1 + p_2} \quad (4)$$

α_{p_1} and α_{p_2} , respectively, are the coefficients of the thermo- electromotive force? caused by the presence of one light and one heavy hole bands. If the electrical conductivity of heavy holes is smaller than that of light holes, p_2 in the denominator of the fraction can be dropped in expression (4).

Furthermore, if $\alpha_{p_2} \cdot p_2 \ll \alpha_{p_1} \cdot p_1 \cdot b'$, then the total thermo- electromotive force, thermo- electromotive force, light holes with a coefficient equal to the coefficient.

Thermo- electromotive force coefficient for a simple parabolic band structure

$$\alpha = \frac{k}{e} \left[\frac{(r+2)F_{r+2}(\eta^*)}{(r+1)F_r(\eta^*)} - \eta^* \right] \quad (5)$$

Here $F_r(\eta^*)$ and $F_{r+2}(\eta^*)$ are Fermi integrals,

$$F_r(\eta^*) = \int_0^\infty \frac{x^r dx}{e^{x-\eta^*} + 1}$$

For a non-degenerate electron gas ($\eta^* < -2$), formula (5) is simplified and the following expression is obtained,

$$\alpha = \frac{k}{e} \left[r + 2 + \ln \frac{2(2\pi mkT)^{3/2}}{h^3 n} \right], \quad (6)$$

Here

$$m = N^{2/3} (m_1 \cdot m_2 \cdot m_3)^{1/3}$$

effective mass of the density of states, N -number of ellipsoids, m_1, m_2, m_3 - are the principal values of the effective mass tensor. Expression (5) is a function of the Fermi energy, which increases until the heavy holes reach the top of the bands, after which it remains constant. This, in turn, causes the thermo- electromotive force coefficient to remain constant.

If $\alpha_{p_2} \cdot p_2$ has a device comparable to $\alpha_{p_1} \cdot p_1 \cdot b'$, then $p_2 \ll p_1 \cdot b'$ (because the mobility of heavy holes is very small) and the thermo- electromotive force coefficient is defined as follows,

$$\alpha = \alpha_{p_1} \left(1 + \frac{\alpha_{p_2} \cdot p_2}{\alpha_{p_1} p_1 b'} \right). \quad (7)$$

This value is greater than α_{p_1} , since the second limit increases with increasing concentration, at its high values, the thermo- electromotive force coefficient increases, with a subsequent increase in the concentration of heavy holes, the thermo- electromotive force coefficient decreases.

As can be seen from the temperature dependence of the carrier mobility, the μ conductivity increases up to 250 K as a result of the scattering of charge carriers by impurity ions in the impurity region, and decreases upon scattering by thermal vibrations. On the whole, the temperature dependences of σ, R, α , and μ confirm each other.

Figure 1. The dependence of the specific electrical conductivity of $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ crystals on temperature: 1- $x=0.01$; 2- $x=0.02$; 3- $x=0.03$; 4- $x=0.04$.

Figure 2. Dependence of the Hall coefficient of $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ crystals on temperature: 1- $x=0.01$; 2- $x=0.02$; 3- $x=0.03$; 4- $x=0.04$.

Figure 3. Temperature dependence of the thermo- electromotive force coefficient of $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ crystals: 1- $x=0.01$; 2- $x=0.02$; 3- $x=0.03$; 4- $x=0.04$

Figure 4. Dependence of the Hall mobility of $\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x\text{Te}$ crystals on temperature: 1- $x=0.01$; 2- $x=0.02$; 3- $x=0.03$; 4- $x=0.04$.

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